

Biological Assessments for Conservation Easements Kenai Peninsula Borough Parcels 04937016 and 04937014

Prepared For Kachemak Heritage Land Trust - Version 1.0 September 2024

Table of Contents

Introduction	2
Site Visit Details	3
Site Maps	3
Photographs	4
General Property Information	5
Freshwater Aquatic Features	5
Terrestrial Wildlife & Habitat	6
Hazardous Sites	7
Invasive Species Evaluation	8
Overall Summary and Narrative	11
Appendix A: Water Quality Field Form	12
Appendix B: 2020 KP-CISMA Invasive Species Lists	13

Introduction

Kachemak Heritage Land Trust (KHLT), a 501(c)3 nonprofit based in Homer, Alaska, conducts due diligence on property parcels as part of its process in designating conservation easement lands throughout the Kenai Peninsula Borough. Biological assessments are an important tool to document ecological conditions at the time of land acquisition. Documenting current conditions allows for continued stewardship to ensure that ecological values can be maintained in perpetuity.

Kenai Watershed Forum (KWF), a 501(c)3 based in Soldotna, Alaska, frequently collaborates with KHLT to perform biological assessments throughout the Kenai Peninsula Borough, performing on-site visits to document parcel conditions. During site visits, staff perform surveys intended to visually assess all or most of the parcel(s) and record relevant observations of wildlife sign, fish habitat, water quality, and other characteristics.

We used a custom protocol to perform initial biological assessments on Kenai Peninsula Borough Parcels 04937014 (35.01 acres) & 04937016 (11.39 acres) located near Soldotna, Alaska in June 2024. We found natural vegetation and aquatic features generally intact with minimal disturbance present. One observation of an invasive bird cherry tree (*Prunus padus*) highlights the need for continued monitoring and treatment of non-native plant species detrimental to fish and wildlife.

This report and its associated photographs and field notes are archived in Zenodo repository [10.5281/zenodo.13743494](https://zenodo.org/record/105281/files/zenodo.13743494).

Site Visit Details

Organization	Date/Time	Observer Names
Kenai Watershed Forum	6/13/2024	Benjamin Meyer Bonnie Bernard Katrina Danzinger Ceili DeMarais

Site Maps

Figure 1. Parcel map of the properties observed, AKEPIC records, and anadromous streams. 2024 observed parcels were the two southern parcels adjacent to Silver Salmon Drive (IDs 04937014 & 04937016). Previous documented infestations of European bird cherry from AKEPIC are represented by red dots.

Photographs

We collected smartphone photographs in the field to visually represent vegetation and topography throughout the parcels. Photos include plant specimens of interest, stream channels, fish specimens, and bird dwellings. In some cases photographs taken with the Solocater app include a watermark with site details, location coordinates, elevation, and directional aspect. All photographs are available for download as a zip file in Zenodo¹ repository 10.5281/zenodo.13743494.

General Property Information

Borough Parcel ID #	Parcel Size (acres)	General Description
04937016	11.39	East (downhill) side of Silver Salmon drive near Soldotna, Alaska
04937014	35.01	West (uphill) side of Silver Salmon drive near Soldotna, Alaska

General notes on assessed parcels: The two parcels in this assessment are nearly contiguous, bisected by the Silver Salmon Dr. right of way corridor. The parcels are in the vicinity of a developing residential area but are nearly free of signs of disturbance impacts. The one exception is a small section of abandoned driveway in the NE corner of parcel 04937016. Vegetation or landscape alteration is otherwise not apparent throughout the properties.

Freshwater Aquatic Features

Borough Parcel ID #	Wetland Extent (%)	Stream Miles (NHD*)	Lake Acres (NHD*)	Salmon Stream Miles (AWC**)	Salmon Lake Acres (AWC**)
04937016	100% (Riverine)	0.12 (see note)	0	0.12 (see note)	0
04937014	~95% (Riverine, Kettle)	0.25	0	0.25	0

* NHD = National Hydrography Database, US Geological Survey

** AWC = Anadromous Waters Catalog, Alaska Dept of Fish and Game

¹ <https://zenodo.org/>

Parcel 04937016 Freshwater Aquatic Features

- 100% coverage by riverine wetlands, as classified by the KWF Wetlands Assessment^{2,3}
- Western edge of parcel parallels the main stem Kenai River for 260 ft
- Long-term water quality data (years 2000 - 2024) for the main stem Kenai River is available from the nearby Pillars boat launch site, as part of Kenai Watershed Forum's Kenai River Baseline Water Quality Monitoring program⁴
- An unnamed stream runs east-west, intermittently inside and outside of the parcel boundary (Alaska Department of Fish and Game Anadromous Waters Catalog Waterbody 244-30-10010-2031). The stream was re-confirmed as anadromous during our site visit with use of minnow traps at the crossing of Silver Salmon Dr.

Parcel 04937014 Freshwater Aquatic Features

- ~95% coverage by wetlands, primarily riverine and as well as kettle in the northern section, as classified by the KWF Wetlands Assessment^{5,6}
- An unnamed stream runs east-west through the center of the parcel (Alaska Department of Fish and Game Anadromous Waters Catalog Waterbody 244-30-10010-2031). The stream was re-confirmed as anadromous during our site visit with use of minnow traps at the crossing of Silver Salmon Dr.

Notes on unnamed stream

- *Lack of parcel boundary alignment with stream path:* The unnamed stream on parcel 04937016's southern border does not align with adjacent parcel boundaries. Additionally, the stream flow path represented by digital arcs in the National Hydrography Database and the Kenai Peninsula Borough's ordinance 21.18 catalog are based on calculated flow paths, with positional accuracy of 167 ft⁷. Finally, digital arcs representing this stream ADF&G's Anadromous Waters Catalog are hand-digitized and are insufficient to accurately represent physical location. In sum, the above caveats suggest any future disturbance activities that may occur near either side of the stream corridor should require an on-site physical survey to confirm zoning boundaries, in light of the 50 ft riparian conservation corridor surrounding streams listed under borough ordinance 21.18.
- *Fish species present:* Using minnow traps baited with cured roe, we observed rearing juvenile coho salmon and juvenile Dolly Varden, consistent with existing ADF&G data⁸. Photos and field notes are archived in Zenodo repository 10.5281/zenodo.13743494. Based on the dimensions of the stream channel it is unlikely that the stream serves as fish spawning habitat, but instead as excellent juvenile rearing habitat.
- *Water quality:* We used a YSI ProQuatro handheld water quality to measure basic water quality parameters on the downstream side of the culvert where the unnamed stream crosses Silver Salmon Drive. On 6/13/2024 at 12:55 PM, we observed the following conditions:
 - Water temperature: 11.1 °C

² <https://www.kenaiwatershed.org/cook-inlet-wetlands/wetland-types/riverine-wetlands/>

³ <https://www.kenaiwatershed.org/news-media/wetlands-on-the-kenai-peninsula/>

⁴ <https://www.kenaiwatershed.org/kenai-river-baseline-water-quality-monitoring/>

⁵ <https://www.kenaiwatershed.org/cook-inlet-wetlands/wetland-types/riverine-wetlands/>

⁶ <https://www.kenaiwatershed.org/news-media/wetlands-on-the-kenai-peninsula/>

⁷ <https://www.usgs.gov/faqs/what-positional-accuracy-national-hydrography-dataset-nhd>

⁸ <https://www.adfg.alaska.gov/sf/SARR/AWC/index.cfm?ADFG=nomSearch.searchSubmit&wid=244-30-10010-2031>

- Dissolved oxygen: 10.45 mg/l
- Specific conductivity: 73.3 uS/cm
- pH: 7.27

Terrestrial Wildlife & Habitat

We recorded informal visual observations of terrestrial wildlife and habitat during the walking surveys performed on both parcels. Highlights of these informal observations include:

- Bear scat was observed on parcel 04937016. Age and species indeterminate.
- Tufts of moose fur were observed on various chest-level tree branches throughout both parcels
- Signs of spruce bark beetle infestation are evident, ~50% of standing spruce is dead
- Several voles (species unknown) were observed swimming across the unnamed stream channel
- Several avian species and their nests were identified by sight and/or sound throughout both parcels, including:
 - Alder flycatcher
 - Northern water thrush
 - Dark eyed junco
 - Wilson's snipe
 - Bald eagle

Hazardous Sites

We examined the Alaska Department of Environmental Conservation's "Alaska DEC Contaminated Sites" map linked at <https://dec.alaska.gov/das/gis/apps/>. We confirmed the absence of active or historical contaminated sites that would be likely to affect conservation values of the parcels. One diesel-spill contaminated site listed in active cleanup status was identified 0.25 miles to the south of parcel 04937014 (44890 Churchill Avenue, Mile 3.5 Kenai Spur Hwy., Kenai, AK 99611)⁹. Public site records do not describe any features of the site that suggest downhill or lateral flow of contaminated groundwater or soils.

Invasive Species Evaluation

Kenai Watershed Forum staff found a small infestation of European bird cherry (*Prunus padus*, or chokecherry) on one LTO parcel (04937136), totalling 0.002 acres in area (Figure 2). This site is located on the north side of an anadromous stream in riparian habitat. A mature chokecherry was found on the west parcel (ID 04937016), along with a handful of 9 saplings. Manual removal of saplings occurred after their presence was noted, but the adult tree was left uncontrolled at the time of survey. European bird cherry are known for their ability to easily invade undisturbed wetlands and other nearby habitats. It has also been documented in the Alaska Exotic Plants Information Clearinghouse (AKEPIC)¹⁰ that there previously has been three sites of European bird cherry across the Kenai River less than 0.25mi from this parcel (occurrence data from AKEPIC, accessed May 28, 2024). In 2023, KWF observed infestations of Oxeye daisy (*Leucanthemum vulgare* Lam.) and Orange hawkweed (*Hieracium aurantiacum* L.) on the KHLT parcel

⁹ <https://dec.alaska.gov/Applications/SPAR/PublicMVC/CSP/SiteReport/1004>

¹⁰ <https://akepic.portal.axds.co/#map/ls/VHRjYDnw>

(04937136) north of the parcels described in this report. Neither of these species were found in surveys described here.

Target Species List

The target species list for this bioassessment was developed by consulting (1) the most recent (2020) Kenai Peninsula Cooperative Invasive Species Management Area (KP-CISMA) priority list; and (2) the AKEPIC 2.0 Map Portal¹¹ to identify nearby infestations that could act as source populations for the parcels being assessed. Taxa were added to the target species list if they were (1) identified on the KP-CISMA priority list and (2) occurred within 2.0 km of the LTO Parcels. Based on these criteria the following plant species were targeted for this bioassessment:

- *Phalaris arundinacea* (reed canarygrass)
- *Prunus padus* (European bird cherry)
- other KP-CISMA priority species if/as encountered

Both European bird cherry and reed canarygrass are categorized as species of ‘Secondary Concern’ by the KP-CISMA– that is, species that are well-established on the Kenai Peninsula but may be suitable for localized eradication efforts. The full priority list is provided as an appendix to this report, and more information regarding the KP-CISMA priority list can be found online at <https://kenaiinvasives.org/resources/>.

Areas Prioritized for Invasive Species Survey

Based on the Kenai Peninsula Borough (KPB) high-resolution imagery layer, KWF identified approximately 0.34 miles of active road (Silver Salmon Drive) and 350 feet of trail or abandoned road running through or directly adjacent to parcels 04937014 and 04937016. Based on the same high-resolution imagery, approximately 0.5 miles of streambank habitat were prioritized for invasive species survey efforts. These habitats are areas of natural disturbance and represent potential habitat for both European bird cherry (*Prunus padus*) and reed canarygrass (*Phalaris arundinacea*). This stream is of particular importance as a conservation feature due its inclusion in the Anadromous Waters Catalog. Relative to native vegetation, stands of *Prunus padus* contribute significantly fewer terrestrial invertebrates to adjacent streams and may thereby negatively impact juvenile salmon forage quality¹². Reed canarygrass is also of concern due to its ability to form dense stands that promote silt deposition and thereby constrict streams¹³.

Invasive Species Field Surveys

KWF maintains an internal digital invasive species survey form that is consistent with minimum AKEPIC reporting standards. This interface is hosted via ArcGIS Online and is accessible to employees via the ESRI Field Maps application. For this biological assessment, all invasive species data, including site photographs,

¹¹ <https://akepic.portal.axds.co/#map>

¹² Roon, D. A., Wipfli, M. S., Wurtz, T. L., & Blanchard, A. L. 2016. Invasive European bird cherry (*Prunus padus*) reduces terrestrial prey subsidies to urban Alaskan salmon streams. *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, 73(11), 1679-1690.

¹³ Lyons, K.E. 1998. Element stewardship abstract for *Phalaris arundinacea* L. Reed canarygrass. The Nature Conservancy, Arlington, Virginia

were collected in the internal form and are summarized below.

Figure 2. Map of invasive species survey efforts and location of the *Prunus padus* infestation detected. GPS survey tracks reflect prioritization of disturbed areas and habitat vulnerable to the target invasive species, *Prunus* spp. and *Phalaris arundinacea*.

Invasive Species Survey Results

Only one infestation of concern was documented during the course of the 13 June 2024 survey. One mature European bird cherry (*Prunus padus*) tree and six seedlings were documented near the southern border of the western LTO parcel (Parcel ID: 04937016; Coordinates: 60.5374, -151.0982). The six seedlings were hand-pulled at the time of detection, but the mature tree is not removable by manual means. The total infested area was mapped as 0.001 acres, representing < 0.001% cover of the 11.4 acre parcel. However, the primary tree's flowers and the surrounding seedlings suggest that the mature tree is actively reproducing and that the infestation may grow over time.

Figure 3. Photos of the *Prunus padus* infestation located on Parcel ID 04937016. This infestation consists primarily of the pictured flowering tree, although six nearby seedlings were detected and removed during this survey.

Overall Summary and Narrative

Kenai Watershed Forum staff performed biological assessments to document ecological conditions on two parcels recently acquired by Kachemak Heritage Land Trust. The KHLT parcels inspected in 2024 were those with KPB Parcel IDs 04937014 and 04937016, which are contiguous with Parcel ID 04937136, for which KWF previously performed a biological assessment in 2023. KWF staff recorded observations of wildlife sign and fish habitat, water quality, and other significant biological characteristics, as well as surveying for invasive species of concern. The two parcels assessed in 2024 contain 43.9 acres of mapped wetland habitat, including 26.5 acres of riverine wetland¹⁴, 17.4 acres of kettle wetland¹⁵, and approximately 2000 ft of an unnamed anadromous stream. Together these three parcels conserve 99 acres along the Kenai River, including 92 acres of wetland habitat. Surveys were conducted by four KWF staff on 13 June 2024 and covered approximately 2.95 km within these parcels along priority habitats including the unnamed anadromous creek, vegetation type transitions, and disturbed areas. Only one invasive species of concern—*Prunus padus*—was detected during assessment. However, as evidenced by the presence of a flowering tree with saplings nearby, the infestation was determined to be spreading. Though the overall cover of this infestation is very low— <0.001% of the parcel— future site visits should include survey effort near this mature tree in order to monitor the spread of the infestation.

¹⁴ <https://www.kenaiwatershed.org/cook-inlet-wetlands/wetland-types/riverine-wetlands/>

¹⁵ <https://www.kenaiwatershed.org/cook-inlet-wetlands/wetland-types/kettle-wetland/>

On these properties, much of the ecological value lies in the unnamed anadromous stream, which was confirmed to host both juvenile coho salmon and Dolly Varden, and in the varied lowland boreal vegetation communities that provide habitat for mammalian and avian wildlife. Specifically, dominant vegetation types for these parcels include black spruce or black spruce-broadleaf forest (58%), transected by more open white/lutz spruce-birch forests (32%) along the unnamed anadromous stream. These “forest edge” ecotones contribute to wildlife diversity and provide excellent habitat, especially for bird species. Bear scat, moose sign, and voles were also detected during the course of the survey.

Appendix A: Water Quality Field Form

APPENDIX A

Kenai Watershed Forum
Portable Water Quality Meter
Field Form

Version 1.0 Updated 4/2/2024

Section A - Sample Event									
Site Arrival Date			Site Depart Date						
Site Arrival Time			Site Depart Time						
Site Name				Latitude					
Crew				Longitude					
Section B - Portable Meter Measurements									
Model	Instru- ment ID	Collection Time (HH:MM)	Observation Time* (HH:MM)	Parameter	Value	Unit	Notes	Rep- licate	
YSI ProQuatro		N/A		pH				1	
				Conductivity					
				DO					
				Temperature					
Hach 2100P**				Turbidity					
YSI ProQuatro		N/A		pH				2	
				Conductivity					
				DO					
				Temperature					
Hach 2100P**				Turbidity					
** TURBIDITY - FOR OFFICE USE ONLY (LEAVE DATA BLANK IN FIELD)									
Section C - Site Photos - OPTIONAL									
Camera ID			Photo ID	Photo Notes					
Section E - General Notes									
					QC1				
					For Office Use	Data Ent			
Side A						QC2			

For questions contact
hydrology@kenaiwatershed.org
www.kenaiwatershed.org

Appendix B: 2020 KP-CISMA Invasive Species Lists

INVASIVE AND NOXIOUS WEED SPECIES CLASSIFICATION (UPDATED April 2020) ¹AKNHP Invasiveness Ranking included

Table 1 is not an all-inclusive list of invasive species, potentially invasive, and established invasive species within the KP-CWMA geography. Rather, this list reflects partner priorities for treatment actions and awareness at this point in time. A more comprehensive list can be found in Appendix B.

Primary Concern (New Invaders, Eradicate from KP-CWMA)	Secondary Concern (Established Invaders, localized eradication)	Potential Invaders to the KP-CWMA
Cheat grass** (78) <i>Bromus tectorum</i>	Narrowleaf hawkbeard (56) <i>Crepis tectorum</i>	Garlic mustard (70) <i>Alliaria petiolata</i>
Elodea spp. (79) <i>canadensis, nuttallii</i>	Quackgrass* (59) <i>Elymus repens</i>	Spotted knapweed (86)* <i>Centaurea stoebe ssp. micranthos</i>
Creeping thistle* (76) <i>Cirsium arvense</i>	Hempnettle* (50) <i>Galeopsis spp.</i>	Crownvetch (68) <i>Coronilla varia (aka Securigera varia)</i>
Bull thistle (61) <i>Cirsium vulgare</i>	Orange hawkweed* (79) <i>Hieracium auranticum</i>	Scotchbroom (69) <i>Cystis scoparius</i>
Wild buckwheat, black bindweed* (50) <i>Fallopia convolvulus</i>	Meadow hawkweed (79) <i>Hieracium caespitosum</i>	Knotweed Species (87) <i>Fallopia bohemicum; F. japonica; F. sachalinensis</i>
Sweetclover (81) <i>Melilotus alba & officinalis</i>	Mouse ear hawkweed (63) <i>Hieracium pilosella</i>	Ornamental jewelweed (82) <i>Impatiens glandulifera</i>
Tansy ragwort (63) <i>Senecio jacobaea</i>	Narrowleaf hawkweed (51) <i>Hieracium umbellatum</i>	Broadleaved pepperweed* (71) <i>Lepidium latifolium</i>
Perennial sowthistle* (73) <i>Sonchus arvensis</i>	Fall Dandelion (51) <i>Leontodon autumnalis</i>	Purple loosestrife* (84) <i>Lythrum salicaria</i>
Common tansy (60) <i>Tanacetum vulgare</i>	Oxeye daisy (61) <i>Leucanthemum vulgare</i>	Eurasian water-milfoil (90) <i>Myriophyllum spicatum</i>
Bird vetch* (73) <i>Vicia cracca</i>	Butter and eggs* (69) <i>Linaria vulgaris</i>	Curly leaved pondweed <i>Potamogeton crispus</i>
	Reed canarygrass (83) <i>Phalaris aurundinacea</i>	Himalayan blackberry (77) <i>Rubus discolor</i>
	Euro. bird cherry/Chokecherry (74) <i>Prunus padus & P. virginiana</i>	Spartina species (86) <i>Spartina alterniflora, S. anglica, S. densiflora, S. patens</i>
	Tall buttercup (60) <i>Ranunculus acris</i>	Western salsify (50) <i>Tragopogon dubius</i>
	Creeping buttercup (72) <i>Ranunculus repens</i>	

*Currently listed as a prohibited or restricted noxious weed by Alaska State Statute (11AAC 34.020)

** Historical record from Kenai National Wildlife Refuge herbarium, 1958. Infestation at Portage Alaska Wildlife Conservation Center, currently managed by Chugach National Forest Service.

¹AKNHP Ranking is an Alaska-specific invasiveness ranking (a high rank indicates greater invasiveness) provided by the Alaska Natural Heritage Program. Current ranking and methodology available at:

https://accs.uaa.alaska.edu/wp-content/uploads/Invasiveness_Ranking_System_for_Non-Native_Plants_Alaska.pdf

**NON-NATIVE PLANT SPECIES RECORDED ON THE KENAI PENINSULA with
Alaska invasiveness ranking of at least 50 and/or noxious weed rating (UPDATED MAY, 2020)**

Invasive plants in Alaska are ranked by local ecologists on an invasiveness scale of 0—100. Invasiveness ranks take into account a species’ ecological impacts, biological characteristics (ability to reproduce and spread), and the feasibility of control. This system is described in the Invasiveness Ranking System for Non-Native Plants of Alaska (Carlson et al. 2008).

How invasive is a plant on the list? Ranks of:

- **80 or higher** are considered “Extremely invasive”
- **70---79** – “Highly invasive”
- **60---69** – “Moderately invasive”
- **50---59** – “Modestly invasive”
- **40---49** – “Weakly invasive”
- **39 or lower** – “Very Weakly Invasive”

According to the Invasiveness Ranking System for Non-Native Plants of Alaska, species ranked 70 and higher are considered to be very threatening to Alaska. Species ranked 50-69 also pose significant risks to Alaska’s ecosystems. Species ranked below 50 are not thought to significantly alter ecosystem processes and plant communities. Only those non-native plants ranked below 50 with a noxious weed designation are included in the table below.

USDA CODE	Latin Name	Noxious Weeds ¹	AK Noxious Weed ²	Common Name	AKNHP RANKING ³
ALPR3	<i>Alopecurus pratensis</i> L. (52)			meadow foxtail	52
BRRA	<i>Brassica rapa</i> L. (50)			field mustard	50
BRINI	<i>Bromus inermis</i> ssp. <i>Inermis</i> (62)			smooth brome	62
BRTE	<i>Bromus tectorum</i> ** (78)	✓		cheatgrass	78
CARA	<i>Campanula rapunculoides</i> L. (64)			rampion bellflower	64
CAAR18	<i>Caragana arborescens</i> (74)			Siberian peashrub	74
CEBI2	<i>Centaurea stoebe</i> ssp. <i>Micranthos</i> (86)	✓		spotted knapweed	86
CIAR4	<i>Cirsium arvense</i> (76)	✓	✓	Canada thistle	76
CIVU	<i>Cirsium vulgare</i> (61)	✓		bull thistle	61
CRETE3	<i>Crepis tectorum</i> (56)			narrowleaf hawkweed	56
CYSC4	<i>Cytisus scoparius</i> (69)	✓		scotch broom	69
DAGL	<i>Dactylis glomerata</i> (53)			orchard grass	53
DIPU	<i>Digitalis purpurea</i> L. (51)			purple foxglove	51
ELODE	<i>Elodea Michx.</i> sp. (79)			elodea waterweed	79
ELRE4	<i>Elymus repens</i> (59)	✓	✓	quackgrass	59
ELSI	<i>Elymus sibiricus</i> L. (53)			Siberian wildrye	53
FACO	<i>Fallopia convolvulus</i> (L.) A. Love (50)			black bindweed	50
jFAJA2	<i>Fallopia japonica</i> (Houtt.) Ronse Decr. (87)			Japanese knotweed	87
GABI3	<i>Galeopsis bifida</i> (50)			splitlip hempnettle	50
GATE2	<i>Galeopsis tetrahit</i> (50)		✓	brittlestem hempnettle	50
HEMA3	<i>Hesperis matronalis</i> L. (41)	✓		dames rocket	41
HIAU	<i>Hieracium aurantiacum</i> (79)	✓		orange hawkweed	79
HICA10	<i>Hieracium caespitosum</i> (79)	✓		meadow hawkweed	79
HIP1	<i>Hieracium pilosella</i> L. (63)	✓		mouseear hawkweed	63
HIUM	<i>Hieracium umbellatum</i> (51)			narrowleaf hawkweed	51
HOJU	<i>Hordeum jubatum</i> (63)			foxtail barley	63

IMGL	<i>Impatiens glandulifera</i> (82)	✓		ornamental jewelweed	82
LEAU2	<i>Leontodon autumnalis</i> L. (51)			fall dandelion	51
LEVU	<i>Leucanthemum vulgare</i> (61)	✓		oxeye daisy	61
LIVU2	<i>Linaria vulgaris</i> (69)	✓	✓	butter and eggs	69
LOPEM2	<i>Lolium perenne</i> spp. <i>Multiflorum</i> (52)			Italian rye grass	52
LOCO6	<i>Lotus corniculatus</i> L. (65)			bird's-foot trefoil	65
LUPOP2	<i>Lupinus polyphyllus</i> Lindl. ssp. <i>Polyphyllus</i> (71)			bigleaf lupine	71
MESAF	<i>Medicago sativa</i> L. ssp. <i>falcata</i> Arcang (64)			yellow alfalfa	64
MEOF	<i>Melilotus officinalis</i> & <i>alba</i> (69)			sweetclover	69
MYSC	<i>Myosotis scorpioides</i> L. (54)	✓		true forget-me-not	54
PHAR3	<i>Phalaris arundinacea</i> (83)			reed canarygrass	83
PHPR3	<i>Phleum pratense</i> (54)			timothy	54
PLMA2	<i>Plantago major</i> (44)		✓	common plantain	44
POAN	<i>Poa annua</i> (46)		✓	annual bluegrass	46
POPRI2	<i>Poa prantensis</i> ssp. <i>Irrigata</i> (52)			spreading bluegrass	52
POPRP2	<i>Poa prantensis</i> ssp. <i>Pratensis</i> (52)			Kentucky bluegrass	52
POTR2	<i>Poa trivialis</i> L. (52)			rough bluegrass	52
PRPA5	<i>Prunus padus</i> (74)			European bird cherry	74
RAACA3	<i>Ranunculus acris</i> var. <i>acris</i> (54)			showy buttercup	54
RARE3	<i>Ranunculus repens</i> (54)	✓		creeping buttercup	54
RORU	<i>Rosa rugosa</i> Thunb. (72)	✓		rugosa rose	72
RUAC3	<i>Rumex acetosella</i> (51)	✓		sheep sorrel	51
RUCR	<i>Rumex crispus</i> (48)	✓		curly dock	48
SEJA	<i>Senecio jacobaea</i> L. (63)	✓		tansy ragwort	63
SEVU	<i>Senecio vulgaris</i> (36)	✓		common groundsel	36
SILAA3	<i>Silene latifolia</i> ssp. <i>alba</i> (42)	✓		bladder campion	42
SOAR2	<i>Sonchus arvensis</i> (73)	✓	✓	perennial sowthistle	73
SOAU	<i>Sorbus aucuparia</i> (59)			European mountain ash	59
TAVU	<i>Tanacetum vulgare</i> (60)	✓		common tansy	60
TAOFO	<i>Taraxacum officinale</i> spp. <i>Officinale</i> (58)			common dandelion	58
TRDU	<i>Tragopogon dubius</i> Scop. (50)			yellow salsify	50
TRHY	<i>Trifolium hybridum</i> (57)			alsike clover	57
TRPR2	<i>Trifolium pratense</i> (53)			red clover	53
TRRE3	<i>Trifolium repens</i> (59)			white clover	59
TRPE21	<i>Tripleurospermum perforata</i> (48)	✓		scentless false mayweed	48
VETH	<i>Verbascum thapsus</i> L. (52)	✓		common mullein	52
VICR	<i>Vicia cracca</i> (73)		✓	bird vetch (tufted vetch)	73

¹Noxious Weeds – Species currently listed as noxious weeds by one or more states in the US (outside of Alaska) according to the USDA Plants Database at <http://plants.usda.gov>

²AK Noxious Weeds – Also currently listed as a noxious weed by Alaska State Statute (11 AAC 34.020)

³AKNHP Ranking is an Alaska-specific invasiveness ranking (a high rank indicates greater invasiveness) provided by the Alaska Natural Heritage Program. Current ranking and methodology available at: <https://accs.uaa.alaska.edu/invasive-species/non-native-plant-species-list/>